

Assessment of Residents of Owerri Metropolis Perception of Radio Messages on Indiscriminate Dumping of Refuse

¹ Chika Onwukwe Akwari, ² Christoher Okebram Diala, ³ Precious Idongesit Mba & ⁴ Oluchi Williams-Etumnu*

¹Department of Public Relations, Imo State University, Owerri

²Department of Mass Communication, Federal Polytechnic Nekede, Owerri

³Department of Mass Communication, Akwa Ibom- State Polytechnic Ikot Osurua

⁴Department of Mass Communication, Imo State University, Owerri

 ORCID:

¹ <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-9109-0096>

² <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-2156-5830>

³ <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-2196-0879>

⁴ <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-4852-778X>

*Corresponding Author: anoruoimma@gmail.com

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Abstract

This study investigated residents of Owerri metropolis' perception of radio messages on indiscriminate dumping of refuse. The study was anchored on social judgment theory. The study adopted the survey research design, using questionnaire as the instrument for data collection. The population consists of 1,105,000 Owerri metropolis residents. The multistage sampling technique was utilised while the data was analysed using bar charts and simple percentages. Findings revealed that many of the respondents in Owerri metropolis are moderately exposed to radio messages on indiscriminate dumping of refuse. Also, a greater number of the respondents (52.1%) perceive that radio messages are great, though they still engage in indiscriminate dumping of refuse. Further findings showed that 181(48.7%) of the respondents still dispose of waste indiscriminately in Owerri metropolis. It was recommended that concerted efforts should be made by those who work in the radio medium to frequently air messages that are designed to raise the consciousness of residents to the danger of indiscriminate dumping of refuse so that they will become more exposed to their messages. The messages designed for the radio medium should be more appealing and persuasive in nature so as to be able to change perceptions positively. Sensitisation should be done by the radio medium and appropriate stakeholders to the environment so that residents should start having a positive attitude towards dumping waste indiscriminately.

Keywords: Perception, radio messages, dumping of refuse, Owerri

Introduction

Globally, millions of tons of municipal solid waste are generated every day. Urban waste management is drawing increasing attention, as it can easily be observed that too much garbage is lying uncollected in the streets, causing inconvenience, environmental pollution, and posing a public health risk (Zia & Devadas, 2008 as cited in Yoda et al., 2014).

The waste management situation in Nigeria has been of great concern worldwide and locally (International Solid Waste Association, 2015). An average Nigerian in his household, establishment and industry encounters some tones of solid waste yearly. Several Nigerians have considered it a cheap method of disposing off their solid waste by setting the mixed waste on fire or even by dumping it indiscriminately in an open place thereby leading to pollution which is very harmful to health (Henderson & Dumbili, 2020). Dumping of waste indiscriminately have attendant effects on communities and society, the effects include sickness and infirmity, environmental pollution. Thus there is always need for different approaches in waste management. Also, illegal dumping also known as “fly dumping”, midnight dumping, or wild cat dumping and roadside dumping, is a major problem in the urban and rural communities in Nigeria (Amusan et al., 2018). It is a significant concern regarding public health and safety, proper values, and quality of life. The concept of illegal dumping or flying waste dumping is primitive in nature and could be traced to era of ignorance, it is an environmental menace that can occur in any abandoned facilities or properties, vacant sites, abandoned industrial or residential facilities (Sankoh & Yan, 2013).

The poor waste management situation in recent years has led to a high incidence of sanitation related illness, such as cholera, intestinal worms and typhoid. These are among the top ten diseases that have been recorded, which raises the alarm of a public health crisis (Yoda et al., 2014). However, the ills of inappropriately disposed municipal solid wastes are quite numerous to be mentioned. Health deterioration, accidents, flood occurrences, and environmental pressures are just a few of the negative effects (Ozabor & Obaro, 2016). Proper waste management is a public benefit and obligation. Improper waste disposal by one individual affects the entire citizenry.

Owerri metropolis, which used to be one of the cleanest areas in Nigeria, has become a shadow of itself in terms of cleanliness; this appears to be as a result of the indiscriminate dumping of refuse. The issue of indiscriminate dumping of refuse has made almost every corner within the metropolis dirty, which in no small measure has contributed to environmental pollution. As a result of the inherent danger that goes with indiscriminate dumping of refuse. This menace will go unabated if the consciousness of people is not drawn to it by sensitising the masses about the health and environmental implications of this act through the media. In drawing this attention radio messages become imperative so as to change perception and attitudes of people towards indiscriminate refuse dumping. Effective health communication is central to promoting healthy living and advances our ability to function expectedly well as a member of the society (Nwanekwu et al., 2025). Despite the efforts by the radio medium in curtailing this menace through their messages, it appears that people are still engaging in the act of indiscriminate dumping of refuse. Could it be that residents perceive these messages as worthless, or could it be that they are not exposed to radio messages on indiscriminate dumping of refuse in Owerri metropolis? Based on this, the study examined residents of Owerri metropolis' perception of radio messages on indiscriminate dumping of refuse.

The specific objectives of this study are to:

1. Find out the extent residents of Owerri metropolis are expose to radio messages on indiscriminate dumping of refuse.

2. Examine the perception of Owerri metropolis residents towards to radio messages radio on indiscriminate dumping of refuse.
3. Find out the attitude of Owerri metropolis residents towards indiscriminate dumping of refuse based on radio messages on indiscriminate dumping of refuse.

Theoretical Framework

The study is anchored on Social judgment theory. This theory explains how an audience processes messages. The new information is compared to existing beliefs and a decision to accept or reject the information is made; it states that you have a statement or message and you accept it or reject it based on your cognitive map (Asemah & Ogwo, 2013; Asemah & Nwammuo, 2017; Asemah & Osife-Kurex, 2018). The theory says that audience-members interpret and judge a message and take a position (Amah et al., 2022). The theory focuses on the internal processes of an individual's judgement with relation to a communicated message. Attitude change is the fundamental objective of persuasive communication; thus, social judgement theory seeks to specify the conditions under which this change takes place and predicts the direction and extent of the attitude change. The key point of the social judgement theory is that attitude change is mediated by judgmental processes and effects. Put differently, persuasion occurs at the end of the process where a person understands a message, then compares the position it advocates to the person's position on that issue.

First, there is the latitude of acceptance, which includes all those ideas that a person finds acceptable. Second, there is the latitude of rejection, which includes all those ideas that a person finds unacceptable. Finally, there is the latitude of non-commitment, which includes ideas for which you have no opinion; you neither accept nor reject these ideas. A person's reaction to a persuasive message depends on his or her position on the topic.

This theory is relevant to this study because it provide the basis for us to understand how people take the message of radio in terms of indiscriminate dumping of refuse in Owerri metropolis.

Method

The survey research design was adopted using the tool of questionnaire to gather data for the study. Survey was deemed appropriate because it will allow the researchers to sample opinions, attitude perceptions on the subject matter under investigation (Etumnu et al., 2025). According to Macrotrends Statistics (2025), Owerri Metropolis has a population of 1,105,000. The sample size was determined using the survey monkey online sample size calculator. See screenshot:

Calculate your sample size

Population Size ⓘ

1105000

Confidence Level (%) ⓘ

95 ▼

Margin of Error (%) ⓘ

5

Feedback

Sample size

385

Therefore the sample size of the study was 385. Copies of questionnaire were distributed to residents of Owerri Metropolis in Imo State using the multistage sampling technique. In the first stage, Owerri which is in cluster is already divided into three namely, Owerri North, Owerri West and Owerri Municipal. In the second stage two communities from each local government area were purposively selected because there is a possibility that they are exposed to radio station messages, they are, Orji, Uratta, Umuguma, Ihiagwa, Umuoyima, and Umuororonjo respectively. In stage three, having six communities the researchers distributed the questionnaire proportionately to the communities selected. Therefore, the researchers gave 64 copies of the questionnaire to respondents in these communities purposively. The researchers used a self-structured questionnaire to gather data that was used in this study. The questions were designed to measure exposure, perception and attitude. The instrument was validated by an expert in the field of communication and media studies in Imo State University, Owerri. The test-retest approach was used to check for internal consistency of the instrument. The scores of the first and second responses from respondents were subjected to Cronbach Alpha statistical procedure using SPSS version 21 and the result showed .89 indicating high reliability of instrument. The researchers used face-to-face approach to collect data within four weeks with the aid of research assistants. The respondents' consents were sought and they were assured that this is purely for academic purpose and that at any time they feel like withdrawing they are free to do so and they were also assured that their identity will remain anonymous. The data were analysed using Bar charts and simple percentages.

Findings

This section deals with data analysis and presentation. Out of 385 copies of questionnaire the researchers distributed 372(96.6%) was retrieved while 13 (3.4%) was not returned. Therefore, 372 copies of the returned questionnaire were used for the analysis.

RQ1: To what extent are residents of Owerri metropolis exposed to radio messages on indiscriminate dumping of refuse?

Fig. 1: Respondents' response on the extent they are exposed to radio messages on indiscriminate dumping of refuse in Owerri metropolis.

Analysis from the above chart shows that many of the respondents in Owerri metropolis are moderately exposed to radio messages on indiscriminate dumping of refuse. This means that 40.8% of the respondents are moderately exposed to radio messages on indiscriminate dumping of refuse.

RQ2: What is the perception of Owerri metropolis residents towards to radio messages radio on indiscriminate dumping of refuse?

Fig. 2: Respondents response on their perception towards radio messages on indiscriminate dumping of refuse.

The above chart show the perception residents have about radio messages on indiscriminate dumping of refuse. According to the analysis as seen in figure 2, 194 (52.1%) respondents are of the perception that the radio messages are great though they still engage in indiscriminate dumping of refuse.

RQ3: What is the attitude of Owerri metropolis residents towards to indiscriminate dumping of refuse based on radio messages on indiscriminate dumping of refuse?

Fig. 3: Respondents response on the attitude of Owerri metropolis residents towards to indiscriminate dumping of refuse based on radio messages on indiscriminate dumping of refuse

Analysis from the above chart reveals that 181(48.7%) of the respondents still dispose waste indiscriminately in Owerri metropolis. This means that majority of the respondents still engage in the act of indiscriminate dumping of refuse.

Discussion

Findings from research question one revealed that many of the respondents in Owerri metropolis are moderately exposed to radio messages on indiscriminate dumping of refuse. From this finding one can infer that audiences are not frequently exposed to radio messages concerning how well one can dispose waste properly. This finding is consistent with the study of Akpoghiran (2015) who revealed that audiences are hardly aware of broadcast media campaigns against waste management and that irregular and poor enlightenment campaigns by the broadcast media on solid waste management can have a way to affect residents disposition towards waste management. Also, the study is in consonance with Akong'o et al (2021) who revealed that lack of focus on strategic messages in managing wastes can lead poor knowledge about waste management practices.

Findings revealed that a greater number of the respondents (52.1%) perceive that radio messages are great though they still engage in indiscriminate dumping of refuse. The other respondents (27.9%) are of the views that the messages are not persuasive in enough to influence them positively. Meanwhile (19.8%) confirmed that the message is just there to fill the airtime space. This study is in tandem with that of Henderson and Dumbili (2020) who found that students perceived plastic waste as malodorous, causing harm to human health and blighting environmental aesthetics. Also the study of Kaoje (2017) revealed that majority of the respondents in Sokoto expressed worries about the indiscriminate littering of the metropolis with waste and a lot of them perceive that residents were responsible for the state of poor sanitation while. This study is consistent with the social judgment theory this study was anchored on.

Findings revealed that 181(48.7%) of the respondents still dispose waste indiscriminately in Owerri metropolis. The finding showed the attitude of respondents and the attitude as revealed by the result of the study is not encouraging as good number admitted they still engage in the act of indiscriminate dumping of refuse. This finding is in agreement with Ngwu (2017) study which revealed that he current unwholesome attitude on waste disposal practices and management system in Nigeria is very worrisome

and poses a classic health communication challenge. Also in line is the study of Amusan et al (2018) who found that some of the factors that affect indiscriminate waste disposal is attitudinal factor, social status, ignorance of the methodology of disposal, lack of waste management facilities among others. However, the finding of Akpoghiran (2015) revealed that irregular and poor enlightenment campaigns by the broadcast media on solid waste management can result to poor attitude to waste management by inhabitants invariably, that is to say that positive attitude towards solid waste management depended on regularly broadcast media enlightenment campaigns. This finding is in consistent with social judgment theory this study was framed on.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the finding, it can therefore be established that residents in Owerri metropolis are moderately exposed to radio messages on indiscriminate dumping of refuse. This level of exposure can be linked to the perception they have about these messages and, ultimately, their attitude towards indiscriminate dumping of refuse. So, in line with the finding, the researchers conclude that the perception and attitude residents have towards indiscriminate dumping of refuse are as a result of the exposure they have to the radio messages.

Based on the findings, it can therefore be recommended that:

1. Concerted efforts should be made by those who work in the radio medium to frequently air messages that are designed to raise the consciousness of residents to the danger of indiscriminate dumping of refuse so that they will become more exposed to their messages.
2. The messages designed by radio medium should be more appealing and persuasive in nature so as to be able to change perception positively.
3. Sensitisation should be done by radio medium and appropriate stakeholders to the environment so that residents should start having positive attitude towards dumping waste indiscriminately.

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